

**COMMENTED READING AS A TRADITIONAL METHOD OF WORK IN
LITERATURE LESSONS**

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ANNOTATION The term “commented reading” first entered the literature as a definition of a teaching method and received a broader interpretation a little later, when some authors (G.I. Belenky, M.A. Shneerson, etc.) included it in the table of contents of their studies covering a holistic analysis, in which commented reading plays a significant role.

Among the active promoters of commented reading should be named M.D. Kocherin. Back in 1952, she proposed studying works through commented reading. “We read small works in their entirety in class and comment on them, and from large works we select the most striking passages that are important for clarifying the ideological meaning of the work.”

Key words: Comments, creativity, changes, analysis, M.D. Kocherin, G.I. Belenky, M.A. Shneerson, OK. Bogomolov.

The comments accompanying the reading, in her opinion, are mainly ideological and stylistic in nature; it is aimed at clarifying the ideological content of the work and the ways of expressing it in language.

In subsequent works by M.D. Kocherina, the commentary is interpreted more broadly: it is not only a stylistic analysis, but also an analysis of image techniques (portrait characteristics, landscape descriptions, etc.). Here the goals of classroom reading are clarified and the role of commented reading in developing the aesthetic taste of students is revealed. [1. p. 38-39]

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In articles by M.D. Kocherina's commented reading is interpreted as a study of the work at two stages. At the first stage, through reading with comments, a primary direct acquaintance with the text occurs, and at the second, after understanding the composition of the work, generalizing conclusions are drawn in a sequence corresponding to the composition of the work.

OK. Bogomolova, in her works on commented reading, focuses on the problem of preliminary familiarization of students with a literary text. The relevance of this issue is convincingly proven in an interesting study by E.V. Kvyatkovsky, who, using extensive material, showed how little prepared high school students are for full independent perception of the text. The methodologist rightly notes that "on the path of students to understanding a literary text, to perceiving the ideological and figurative richness of a literary work, there are a large number of obstacles: little life experience, little general and speech culture, inability to think abstractly, to

distinguish the manifestation of the general in an individual, insufficient preparation for figurative perception of reality...". In this regard, he considers it necessary to prepare students for the first reading and assigns a large role to reading with comments: the teacher reads and comments on the text; independent reading of students alternates with commented reading by the teacher; The teacher's comment follows after his expressive reading of the text. [2. p. 239]

Thus, in the 50 - s, an active search began for ways to study works of art that would not destroy the emotional attitude to the artistic word and would ensure the active development of students' creative thinking.

In recent years, the method of commented reading has become widespread in schools as one of the most effective methods of analyzing a work of art.

This type of reading is usually used in high school. It requires intensive and deep preparation of the teacher. If in the lower grades the teacher must comment on words new to students, then in the older grades a more in-depth commentary is required: cultural, with elements of information on history, philosophy, ideologically deep and thorough. Such a comment always enriches students' perception of the text and creates positive motivation for learning.

Commented reading contributes to a deeper penetration into the ideological and artistic fabric of the work, therefore the lessons of commented reading can undoubtedly be called lessons in learning to read skillfully. By drawing students' attention to artistic details, to the landscape, to portraits of characters, to the peculiarities of language, to the writer's thoughts, to the subtext of the work, the teacher teaches thoughtful reading, and this has a positive effect on the quality of schoolchildren's reading. In essays and answers, they learn to express their own opinions and acquire the ability to critically evaluate any literary work. Commented reading lessons teach you to think independently and understand works of art, develop artistic taste and a flair for language.

The vocabulary and general range of ideas of many schoolchildren is relatively small, their knowledge of history is insufficient, so it is hardly possible to

find in the school curriculum a work whose main material would be understandable to students without explanations from the teacher. Often, students, having studied a work, know its content in general, determine (by repeating the textbook and teacher) its ideological meaning, evaluate the characters, but do not understand the meaning of a number of words, expressions, and, consequently, the text itself. For example, children without the help of a teacher will never be able to explain the allegorical meaning of the conversation between the “counselor” and the owner of the inn (A.S. Pushkin “The Captain’s Daughter”, chapter 2). Hence the indifference of schoolchildren to incomprehensible works and their inexpressive reading.

Of course, working on the text of a work of art is complex and varied. These include classes in expressive reading, memorization, retellings, which are sometimes useful to practice in high school, analytical conversations accompanied by citations, and written answers to questions. But one of the most important methods of working on a text is still commented reading.

Commented reading is organically intertwined with other forms of work on the text, in particular with independent reading, during which the skills acquired in the lessons of commented reading of the text are consolidated. It is predominant in the eighth grade, where students are first introduced to a historical and literary course, work on complex works, and learn to write essays. It is especially necessary for poorly prepared students.

The methods of commented reading change depending on the specifics of the work being studied and as the students grow: the degree of their independence in a school with the Kyrgyz language of instruction increases, the problem-based method of study is more actively used, and the ideological and stylistic analysis of the text of the work is deepened.

Thus, in school teaching practice the method of commented reading of the text is traditionally used; it helps students to better understand the work being studied. But new methods of educational commentary on the text, which will be discussed

below, can partially solve the problem of in-depth study of a literary text and interest students in the process of comprehending the work.

Only careful commentary on the text will help students deeply understand the work they are studying. [3. p. 81-82]

For many eighth grade students, the method of commented reading turns out to be the most effective way to perceive and comprehend a literary work; schoolchildren master the literature program more successfully than those who do not read the text with commentary. Undoubtedly, in a school with a non-Russian language of instruction, such reading takes a lot of time. But as experience shows, after such work, two or three final lessons are enough and students themselves can draw conclusions and generalizations.

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